

IR and Raman Spectra of Some Ferrocene Derivatives. Torsional Barriers and Thermodynamic Functions

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The IR and Raman spectra of gaseous $(C_5H_5)_2Fe(C_5H_4COCH_3)$ and $(C_5H_4COCH_3)_2Fe$ were recorded in the frequency range 20–4000 cm^{-1} . Both the gaseous complexes show a Raman absorption at $41 \pm 2 cm^{-1}$ which was assigned to the torsional frequency $\omega_{0,1}$. In these molecules a barrier of $1000 \pm 100 cal/mol$ restricts the rotation of the cyclopentadienyl ring with respect to the rigid frame. The thermodynamic functions of the gaseous ferrocenes are reported in the temperature range 298–450K.

AS part of our ongoing program concerned with the investigations of organometallic compounds, the IR and Raman spectra of the ferrocene derivatives $(C_5H_5)_2Fe(C_5H_4COCH_3)$ and $(C_5H_4COCH_3)_2Fe$ were carried out. The principal aim of our work was to calculate the rotational barriers of these molecules and to compare them with the value determined for ferrocene¹⁻³ and other metallocenes of transition metals⁴⁻⁷. It is in fact highly interesting from a spectroscopic point of view to understand the influence of the substitution of an atom or the addition of a group on the torsional barriers. Recent studies allowed the evaluation of the barriers of restricted rotation of solid and gaseous molecules as dicyclopentadienyl chloride of titanium, zirconium and hafnium^{4,5}, cyclopentadienyl chloride of titanium⁵, cyclopentadienyl trihalides of germanium⁶ and methyltitanium trihalides⁷. From these investigations it was concluded that no significant changes occur, in the limit of the experimental errors, in the height of the barriers when different halides are linked to the central atom as in the $(C_5H_5)_2MX_3$ systems ($M=Ti, Ge$; $X=Cl, Br, I$) and when the C_5H_5 ring is bound to various metals as in the above mentioned complexes and in the $(C_5H_5)_2MCl_2$ molecules^{4,5} ($M=Ti, Zr, Hf$). Therefore, it is interesting to study the behaviour of the rotational barriers of the ferrocenes considered in this work, being the substitution directly carried out, on the five-membered ring.

Experimental

The samples are commercial products (99.95% purity degree) supplied by Koch-Light Laboratories.

The IR spectra were recorded in the range 20-4000 cm^{-1} by using a Perkin-Elmer 180 IR grating spectrophotometer. The Raman spectra were run by a Cary Raman 81 spectrometer equipped

with a He-Ne Laser as exciting source. Resistively heated stainless steel cells, 30 cm pathlength, were employed to record the spectra of the gaseous compounds. The cells were kept at 400 K during the spectroscopic measurements; iron-constantan thermocouples were used at temperature monitors. The cells were filled with nitrogen at one atm. as a gas diffusion barrier and to avoid the condensation of the vapours on the optical windows. The IR and Raman spectra of the solid samples were recorded both at room and cryogenic temperatures (77 and 4.2 K); in the latter case a conventional cryostat working with liquid nitrogen and helium as cooling media was employed. High pressure Raman spectra were run in the gas phase at 5 atm. in order to reveal the torsional fundamentals. The IR and Raman frequencies are accurate in the gas phase within to $\pm 2 cm^{-1}$ and $\pm 1 cm^{-1}$ in the solid phase.

Results and Discussion

The IR and Raman spectra of the investigated compounds show the characteristic features of the ferrocenes derivatives^{8,9} consisting of the appearance in the IR spectra of some of the g-type bands of ferrocene, otherwise only Raman active and of most of the A_{1g} , A_{2g} and E_{2g} modes inactive in the D_{5d} symmetry. The presence of the $COCH_3$ group, in fact, causes the lowering of the molecular symmetry of ferrocene from D_{5d} (staggered conformation) to the inferior symmetries. Accordingly the breakdown of the selection rules of the highest symmetry should be inevitable. Often the study of the spectra of metallocenes is made easy using the approximation of the local symmetry^{9,10}. It must be pointed out, however, that the selection rules of the local symmetry are not always followed, so that IR or Raman modes can appear in both the spectra. According to this approximation, the cyclopentadienyl vibrations regarded under the C_{5v} local

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symmetry⁴ are distributed as $3A_1 + A_2 + 4E_1 + 6E_2$. As regards the substituted ring, although the single $C_6H_4COCH_3$ unit is nominally a C_6 symmetry, its molecular symmetry is raised to C_{2v} if the $COCH_3$ group is considered freely rotating. Therefore, its fundamentals are distributed as $9A_1 + 3A_2 + 8B_1 + 4B_2$. The description of the ring vibrations is reported in Table 1 which also indicates their origin

by the out-of-plane and in-plane ring- $COCH_3$ bendings and ring- $COCH_3$ stretching respectively for the $C_6H_4COCH_3$ unit. The skeletal modes, which involve the metal atom motions, belong to the following symmetry species under the D_{6d} symmetry: $A_{1g} + A_{1u} + A_{2u} + E_{1g} + 2E_{1u}$. These modes are described in Table 2 where the vibrations

TABLE 1—DESCRIPTION OF THE RING VIBRATIONS IN TERMS OF LOCAL SYMMETRIES

C_6H_6 (C_{6v})	$C_6H_4COCH_3$ (C_{2v})	Vibration ^a
A_1 (IR, R) ^b	A_1 (IR, R) ω_1	ν CH
	B_2 (IR, R) ω_2	γ CH
	A_1 (IR, R) ω_3	breathing
A_2 (ia) ^b	B_1 (IR, R) ω_4	δ CH
	A_1 (IR, R) ω_5	ν CH
E_1 (IR, R)	B_1 (IR, R) ω_{5a}	ν CH
	B_1 (IR, R) ω_{5b}	δ CH
	A_1 (IR, R) ω_{6a}	γ CH
	B_1 (IR, R) ω_{6b}	γ ring- $COCH_3$
	A_2 (R) ω_{7a}	ν CC
	B_2 (IR, R) ω_{7b}	ν CH
E_2 (R)	A_1 (IR, R) ω_{8a}	ν ring- $COCH_3$
	B_1 (IR, R) ω_{8b}	δ CH
	B_1 (IR, R) ω_{9a}	δ ring- $COCH_3$
	A_1 (IR, R) ω_{9b}	γ CH
	B_2 (IR, R) ω_{10a}	ν CC
	B_1 (IR, R) ω_{10b}	δ CC
	A_1 (IR, R) ω_{11a}	γ CC
	B_2 (IR, R) ω_{11b}	
	A_1 (IR, R) ω_{12a}	
	B_1 (IR, R) ω_{12b}	
	A_1 (IR, R) ω_{13a}	
	B_1 (IR, R) ω_{13b}	
	A_2 (R) ω_{14a}	
	B_2 (IR, R) ω_{14b}	

(a) ν =stretching, δ =in-plane deformation, γ =out-of-plane deformation.

(b) IR=infrared active, R=Raman active, ia=inactive.

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENT OF THE OBSERVED IR AND RAMAN BANDS

C_6H_6	ring vibrations	$C_6H_4COCH_3$	ring vibrations	Assignment ^a
IR	R	IR	R	
(cm^{-1})	(cm^{-1})	(cm^{-1})	(cm^{-1})	
3110	3110	3110	3110	ω_1
807	806	777	777	ω_2
1112	1110	1045	1044	ω_3
1255 ^b	1255 ^b	1260 ^b	1260 ^b	ω_4
3085	3085	3120	3120	ω_{5a}
		3090	3090	ω_{5b}
		1050	1050	ω_{6a}
1015	1015	980	982	ω_{6b}
		788	320	ω_{7a}
			290	ω_{7b}
1425	1426	1445	1444	ω_{8a}
		1410	1410	ω_{8b}
	3055	3070	3068	ω_{9b}
	1170	1000	1001	ω_{9a}
		222	221	ω_{10a}
		205	204	ω_{10b}
	1071		1019	ω_{11a}
		987	989	ω_{11b}
	1555	1620	1620	ω_{12a}
		1533	1535	ω_{12b}
	897	850	852	ω_{13a}
		887	888	ω_{13b}
	556		567	ω_{14a}
		320	322	ω_{14b}
300	300	298	298	ν_s Fe-Ring
	41 ^c		41 ^c	torsion
475	475	470	471	ν_a Fe-Ring
380	378	371	370	
165	166	145	145	Ring tilt
490	490	311	310	
		CH ₃ internal modes		
	2911	2907	2906	ν_s CH
	2940	2942	2933	ν_a CH
	2965	2964	2955	
	1390	1378	1377	δ -CH ₃
	1470	1469	1465	δ_a CH ₃
	1460	1457	1456	
	1025	1023	1018	ρ CH ₃
		COCH ₃ vibrations		
	1698	1698	1687	ν CO
	1677	1677	1673	
	1222	1222	1220	ν CCH ₃
	650	649	645	δ CO
	715	717	718	
	510	511	509	γ CO
	350	350	355	
	666	666	665	δ CH ₃
	520	520	520	γ CH ₃

(a) The further vibrations are: ν CO, ν CCH₃, δ CO, γ CO, δ CH₃, γ CH₃; s=symmetric, a=antisymmetric, ρ =rocking.

(a) See Tables 1 and 2.

(b) Observed in the IR and Raman spectra at high pressure or at low temperatures (see text).

(c) Observed in the Raman spectra at high pressures or at low temperatures (see text).

to the normal modes of the unsubstituted ring. The $\omega(7b)$, $\omega(9a)$ and $\omega(10b)$ vibrations are replaced

related to the ring-COCH₃ group are also summarized. The assignment of the IR and Raman bands observed in the gas phase spectra is reported in Table 3; it was performed by comparing the present results with the previous ones reported for similar complexes^{5,9-12}. The IR and Raman frequencies corresponding to the C₅H₅ and C₅H₄COCH₃ ring vibrations were found to be coincident, in the limit of the experimental errors, for both the compounds, so that they are not referred in Table 3 to a particular complex.

The spectroscopic expectations based on the approximation of the local symmetries are fulfilled in case of the ring vibrations. The skeletal modes do not follow the selection rules of the D_{5d} symmetry group displaying both IR and Raman activity. Particularly interesting is the discussion of the assignment of the CH in-plane deformation and of the torsional mode. The former vibration should be inactive according to the selection rules of the C_{5v} local symmetry of the five-membered ring while it is expected IR and Raman active in case of the substituted ring (see Table 1). The position of this band in the vibrational spectrum of ferrocene was established by normal coordinate calculations¹³ at 1200 cm⁻¹. This band was observed at 1256 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum ferrocene at low temperature⁵ and its appearance would arise from a second order phase transition. It is also present in the IR and Raman spectra of other cyclopentadienyls⁴⁻⁶ at cryogenic temperatures and in the gas phase at high pressures^{5,6}. The spectra of the two complexes show no absorption in this region; this fact is surprising since one substituted ring is at least present in each molecule. This behaviour most probably seems due to the weakness of this vibration in the gas phase. However, working at high pressure (nitrogen at 5 atm) and at low temperature (77 and 4.2 K) in the gas and solid phases respectively; we were able to reveal this absorption in the IR and Raman spectra of both the ferrocenes at ca. 1260 cm⁻¹.

The internal rotation mode for these complexes is expected in the low region, not very far from the corresponding ferrocene frequency⁵. Our spectra do not indicate the presence of bands in the far IR and Raman. The torsional overtones have revealed a powerful mean^{6,7,14} to evaluate the torsional fundamental $\bar{\omega}_{0,1}$. The Raman spectra recorded in the gas phase show absorptions at 81, 75 and 69 cm⁻¹ (see Fig. 1) which could be assigned to the $\bar{\omega}_{0,2}$, $\bar{\omega}_{1,3}$ and $\bar{\omega}_{2,4}$ overtones respectively. If this assignment is correct, the following set of equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\omega}_{0,2} &= 2\bar{\omega}_e(1 - 3x_e) \\ \bar{\omega}_{1,3} &= 2\bar{\omega}_e(1 - 5x_e) \\ \bar{\omega}_{2,4} &= 2\bar{\omega}_e(1 - 7x_e)\end{aligned}$$

will provide the $\bar{\omega}_e$ and x_e values and through the equation

$$\bar{\omega}_{0,1} = \bar{\omega}_e(1 - 2x_e)$$

Fig. 1. Raman spectra of gaseous⁷ (C₅H₅)₂Fe(C₅H₄COCH₃)₂ in the range 20-100 cm⁻¹. (a) 1.0 atm of N₂, (b) 5.0 atm of N₂.

the torsional fundamental $\bar{\omega}_{0,1}$ is evaluable. Our calculations yield as $\bar{\omega}_{0,1}$ the frequency at 42 cm⁻¹. In order to check this conclusion, we recorded the Raman spectra of the ferrocenes at different pressures of nitrogen (up to 5 atm). High pressure Raman spectroscopy was already employed to reveal the torsional fundamentals^{6,7,14}. Under these conditions we observed a Raman band at 41 ± 2 cm⁻¹ for both the complexes (see Fig. 1) supporting the correctness of our assignment. A further test was carried out recording the Raman spectra of the solid samples at cryogenic temperatures (77 and 4.2 K). Previous studies^{6-7,14} indicate that internal rotation frequencies can also be detected in the solid phase at low temperatures. In this case a band at 42 ± 1 cm⁻¹ was revealed for the investigated species. Similar experiments were performed in the far IR but with no success; it is in fact well known that these vibrations occur with negligible dipole moment changes so that the intensity of the IR bands are very feeble¹⁴.

Rotational barriers and thermodynamic functions:

The barriers of hindered rotation were calculated employing the equation¹⁴:

$$V(\text{erg}) = \frac{8\pi^2 c^2 \bar{\omega}_{0,1}^2 I(r)}{n^2}$$

where $\bar{\omega}_{0,1}$ is the experimental torsional fundamental, $I(r)$ the reduced moment of inertia and n the order of the five-fold barrier. For both the complexes a barrier of 1000 ± 100 cal/mol was found; the associated uncertainty was estimated taking into account an error of ± 2 cm⁻¹ in the frequency measurements due to the broadness of the Raman absorption and the evaluation of the reduced moment of inertia. It was calculated for each molecule employing the same structural parameters of ferrocene³ while the bond lengths and angles of the COCH₃ group were assumed as the sum of the covalent radii of the linked atoms and equal to 120° respectively; the HCH angles of the methyl were considered tetrahedral.

The thermodynamic functions of the gaseous complexes were calculated using the standard

method of statistic thermodynamics^{1,5}. The requested contributions to the partition function were evaluated employing the structural parameters assumed as already reported in the text and the vibrational frequencies summarized in Table 3. Only the electronic ground state was considered in these calculations and it was kept as a singlet^{1,5}. The corrections for the internal rotation contribution were carried out according to the Pitzer treatment^{1,5} on the ground of the calculated barrier $V=1000\pm 100$ cal/mol. The thermodynamic functions are listed in Table 4. The associated errors reported there are based on the uncertainty of ± 2 cm⁻¹ in the frequency values and on the estimation of the molecular parameters.

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF THE GASEOUS FERROCENE DERIVATIVES

T (K)	$S_T^0 - (G_T^0 - H_T^0)/T$ (C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Fe(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃) ₂			$S_T^0 - (G_T^0 - H_T^0)/T$ (C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃) ₂ Fe		
	(e. u.) ^a	(e. u.) ^a	(cal/mol)	(e. u.) ^a	(e. u.) ^a	(cal/mol)
298.15	95.08	70.76	7252	96.52	71.95	7324
300	95.43	70.90	7361	96.87	72.09	7432
325	99.89	72.91	8769	101.33	74.10	8848
350	103.83	74.91 ₅	10122	105.27	76.11	10206
375	107.33	76.92	11406	108.77	78.11 ₅	11496
400	110.45	78.93	12607	111.89	80.12	12706
425	113.22	80.94	13721	114.66	82.13 ₅	13823
450	115.70	82.94 ₅	14739	117.14	84.14	14850
	± 0.25	± 0.25	± 10	± 0.25	± 0.25	± 10

^a e. u. = cal/mol K.

Conclusions :

The rotational barriers of the ferrocenes considered in this study are quite close to the value derived for ferrocene^{1,3}. In the light of these results we are led to conclude that the presence of one or two COCH₃ groups bound to the five-membered ring do not considerably alter the height of the torsional barrier of ferrocene. The conviction that these barriers almost exclusively depend on the nature of the metal-ligand bond is strengthened by the comparison between the present results and the previous ones⁴⁻⁷. For this purpose, the rotational barriers determined by spectroscopic data for a series of systems have been reported in Table 5. As a further development of our research program, we believe it would be interesting to verify the influence on the rotational barriers of strongly electronegative substituents or large size

TABLE 5—SUMMARY OF THE TORSIONAL BARRIERS DERIVED FROM SPECTROSCOPIC DATA

Compound	V(cal/mol)	References
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Fe	900 ± 300	1-4
(C ₅ H ₅)Fe(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃)	1000 ± 100	this work
(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃) ₂ Fe	1000 ± 100	this work
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ TiCl ₂	970 ± 100	4, 5
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ ZrCl ₂	930 ± 100	4, 5
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ TiCl ₂	380 ± 30	5
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ GeCl ₂	390 ± 30	6
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ GeBr ₂	370 ± 30	6
(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ GeI ₂	370 ± 30	6
(CH ₃)TiCl ₃	1500 ± 100	7
(CH ₃)TiBr ₃	1400 ± 100	7
(CH ₃)TiI ₃	1350 ± 100	7

groups directly linked to one or both the cyclopentadienyl rings.

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